

Exploring the Need for Speech and Language Therapy Services in Turkish Schools: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract: Speech and language therapy (SLT) services are vital in assisting children with speech, language, or communication disorders. However, various barriers limit the provision of this service in an equal and adequate manner. This study examines these barriers in the UK, the USA, Canada, Australia, and Türkiye and explores how school-based speech and language therapies contribute to removing these barriers in these countries. Key barriers, including workforce shortages, equity, accessibility, geographical and financial constraints, and lengthy waiting lists, impact the quality and provision of SLT services. Embedding SLT services within the school may provide timely, targeted, and sustainable interventions, thereby improving accessibility and availability. A qualitative comparative method was employed to analyze service provision in the five countries and identify differences and similarities in barriers to accessing SLT services. The findings indicate that while improvements are needed in all countries, Türkiye faces unique challenges that require comprehensive reforms, as there are relatively few speech and language therapists. The service is not accessible for many children, which perpetuates these barriers. Establishing school-based SLT services and integrating relevant training into teacher education curricula should be prioritized, as this will equip future educators with the knowledge and competencies for their active support.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dil ve konuşma terapisi (DKT)
Engeller
Okullarda dil ve konuşma terapisi hizmeti
İletişim bozukluğu

Türk Okullarında Dil ve Konuşma Terapisi Hizmetlerine Duyulan İhtiyacın İncelenmesi: Karşılaştırmalı bir Analiz

Özet: Dil ve Konuşma Terapisi (DKT) dil veya iletişim bozukluğu olan çocuklara destek sağlamada hayati role sahiptir. Ancak birtakım engeller bu hizmetin eşit ve yeterli bir şekilde sunulmasını sınırlamaktadır. Bu çalışma İngiltere, Amerika, Kanada, Avustralya ve Türkiye’deki bu engelleri incelemekte ve okullarda sunulan dil ve konuşma terapisinin bu engellerin kaldırılmasına nasıl katkıda bulunduğunu araştırmaktadır. İş gücü yetersizliği, eşitlik, erişilebilirlik, coğrafi ve finansal engellerle ve uzun bekleme listeleri gibi temel engeller dil ve konuşma terapisi hizmetinin kalitesini ve sunumunu etkilemektedir. Dil ve konuşma terapisi hizmetlerinin okul sistemine entegre edilmesi zamanında, amaca uygun ve sürdürülebilir müdahaleler sağlayabilir, ve erişilebilirlik ve ulaşılabilirliği artırabilir. Bu beş ülkedeki hizmet sunumunu analiz etmek ve bu hizmete erişimdeki engellerin benzerlik ve farklılıklarını tanımlamak için karşılaştırmalı nitel veri analizi yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, bütün ülkelerde iyileştirmelere ihtiyaç duyulduğunu gösterirken, Türkiye’nin kapsamlı reformlar gerektiren benzersiz zorluklarla karşı karşıya olduğunu göstermektedir çünkü dil ve konuşma terapisti sayısı diğer ülkelere göre çok daha azdır ve bu servis çoğu çocuk için ulaşılabilir değildir, bu durum engellerin kalıcılığına neden olmaktadır. Okullarda dil ve konuşma terapisi hizmetinin sunulması ve ilgili eğitimlerin öğretmen eğitimi müfredatlarına eklenmesi öncelikli hale gelmelidir, bu yaklaşım gelecekteki öğretmenleri aktif destekleri için gerekli bilgi ve becerilerle donatacaktır.

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1. Introduction

Communication is an essential skill and foundation for lifelong learning, beginning in early periods and continuing throughout life; people of all ages require this skill (Public Health England, 2020; Senate Community Affairs References Committee, 2014). The ability to communicate is also part of personality as it is a cornerstone of independence, enabling individuals to articulate their ideas, interact in social life autonomously, and navigate the challenges of daily life. Communication involves receiving, comprehending, and expressing oneself using language appropriately to achieve social, emotional, and academic goals and enhance self-esteem (Bercow, 2008; Conway et al., 2022). However, communication is not a universal skill that everyone can gain similarly, and in addition to this, many individuals face challenges that hinder their ability to communicate effectively. Developmental and cognitive differences, such as speech, language, and communication disorders, can limit an individual's communication abilities in various aspects of language, including form, function, and content (Bishop et al., 2017; Blosser, 2024). Specific patterns in children's language development are critical and can serve as an alarming signal for later stages; professional intervention may become necessary when these are not achieved (Public Health England, 2020).

Language disorders reveal abnormal development in comprehension and use of both spoken and written symbols, which children experience in middle childhood or beyond. These disorders can affect children's social interactions and school achievement (Bishop et al., 2017). These disorders can lead to negative outcomes, including difficulty in hearing, reading, language processing, curriculum access, initiating and sustaining social interactions, and even exhibiting behavioral issues such as extreme disruptive behavior and delinquency (Anderson et al., 2016; Bercow, 2008).

Communication disorders are functional outcomes of a disability in receiving, processing, and transmitting the symbols representing language concepts. Their implications are profound, as they often lead to dependence, social isolation, and a higher risk of unemployment, especially when individuals struggle to navigate cognitive, social, and linguistic challenges (Bercow, 2008; Bishop et al., 2017; Bacon, 2001; Blosser, 2024). Early intervention is crucial in preventing long-term academic and social disadvantages, as children starting school without adequate communication skills are at a disadvantage in participating in classroom activities, reading, and social engagement (Blosser, 2024; Bishop et al., 2017; Clegg, 2001; Wright, 1996). Children with a speech or communication disorder can be evaluated among the most vulnerable members of communities; they have less ability to demonstrate positive behaviors like better transition, lower recidivism, and increased participation in youth activities, which can sometimes lead to dropout (Anderson et al., 2022; Monteleone, 2019). Timely and appropriate interventions are crucial to address these challenges, as language disorders are linked to negative outcomes (Anderson et al., 2016).

Speech and language therapy (SLT) is a critical service for children with linguistic and communication disorders, addressing the issues that prevent them from overcoming language delays and impairments. It aims to enhance their educational, social, and personal development, increasing independence and contributing to early diagnosis and evaluation. Through that way, SLT can improve their cognitive, social, and personal development and, address cognitive communication difficulties and swallowing problems, assist students with language delays and impairments to make up for their deficiencies that occur intellectually or physically from infancy to later periods of life (ASHA, 2001; Bishop et al., 2017; Farquharson et al., 2022; Gleissner, 2018; Lawton, 2023). Additionally, SLTs support students in

developing the oral language skills necessary for literacy and comprehension, increasing awareness of sounds and words, comprehending the semantics and syntax of the language, and understanding the discourse coherence of spoken and written texts (ASHA, 2001; McLeod & McKinnon, 2010). Despite their importance, the need for SLT provision in schools, particularly in Turkey, remains underexplored. This study aims to investigate the current state of SLT services in Turkish schools, identify gaps in provision, and emphasize the importance of integrating these services into the educational system to support students with language and communication challenges.

1.1. Rationale Behind the Study

Speech and language therapists play a vital role in supporting children with communication impairments; however, considerable barriers hinder access to their services. These barriers include lack of services, travel distance, waiting lists, limited speech therapist options, lack of public transport, unawareness of SLT services, too many caseloads, government funding, insufficient number of graduates, therapist training, limited employment opportunities and the funding for clinical research, insufficient advertising of the services, lack of timely advice, cultural variations, geographic distance, low public awareness, financial barriers, limited internet access, lower socioeconomic status, age, physical and mental disorders, under education, poverty, immigration challenges, child maltreatment, and inadequate health insurance (Mahendra et al., 2009; Monteleone, 2019). These barriers mainly affect children from logistically disadvantaged areas where limited healthcare access worsens their situation.

When speech and communication disorders are left untreated, it leads to poor academic performance, social, emotional, and mental problems, dependence on welfare, and burden to carers. Additionally, speech and communication impairments can lead to low self-confidence, increased risk of bullying, and unemployment (Lawton, 2023). They experience a disadvantage in forensic interviews as they may struggle to narrate events (Cronin, 2017; McCormack & Verdon, 2015; McKinnon et al., 2007; McLeod et al., 2010). The provision of SLT in a school setting ensures students with language and communication disorders receive the necessary assistance and goal-oriented support consistently, improves accessibility, and promotes their academic progress and classroom equity (Daniel & McLeod, 2017; Just et al., 2022; Lawton, 2023).

Various studies support the integration of SLT in schools; for example, Lee et al.'s study (2021) revealed that 94.5% of parents support in-school therapy. They found that SLT in nurseries helps with adaptation in school, contributes to academic performance and peer interaction, reduces service gaps, lowers costs, and improves children's social communication skills through early intervention in educational settings. Jesus et al. (2017) developed a methodology for SLT services to bridge the gap between children who can and cannot access this service. They formed a team of speech-language therapists (SLTs) to support nursery and primary school students. They diagnosed children with DLD or other disorders and analyzed the functional communication skills of the participants both in the schools and clinics. They achieved a 95% success rate through interventions. Edgar and Rosa-Lugo (2007) examined the working conditions and perceptions of SLTs working in the school setting in Florida. They found that the advantages of school-based speech and language therapy outweigh the disadvantages and contribute to the longevity and retention of speech-language therapists (SLTs) in this setting. Uysal and Gülşah (2018) researched the awareness of candidate teachers on speech and language disorders in the school context. They found

that the participants supported collaboration between speech-language therapists (SLTs) and teachers. They said teachers can meet a child with a speech and language disorder in schools.

Kirby et al. (2018) implemented a 12-month SLT service-learning program, monitoring 122 kindergarteners from the country's remote areas, and identified children with impairments ranging from mild to severe problems. They found that 34% had speech delays, 17% had language delays, 17% had phonological delays, and 5% had awareness delays. After this service, 17% of them have reached age-appropriate developmental standards. Navsaria et al. (2011) examined students' written language difficulties about SLT implications in Cape Town. Their study suggests that SLTs should be involved in the policy-making process related to linguistic processes, provide services in mainstream schools, collaborate with teachers in diagnosing and treating children, especially during the early intervention process, assist in planning and teaching stages of language classes, and support the development of students' general communication skills. These studies show the crucial need for SLT services in the school context.

1.2. The Historical Development of Speech and Language Therapy Services

Speech and language therapy is a relatively new discipline worldwide. The first SLTs were professionals from other fields and teachers interested in assisting individuals with language disorders, not clinicians (Gleissner, 2018). Speech, language, hearing, and communication disorders have been present since the early periods of humankind, but rehabilitation services for children emerged in the 20th century. In 1925, the challenges faced by individuals with speech and language disorders were highlighted through the recognition by the American Academy of Speech Correction, which led to the development of programs to assist the most severe cases, such as those involving deafness (Blosser, 2024). On the other hand, neurologists, surgeons working on the ear, nose, and throat, and teachers helped soldiers with head injuries during WWII, which increased the demand for specialized rehabilitation. The awareness of the crucial role of SLT increased in the USA accordingly (Enderby & Emerson, 1996). Before speech and language therapy emerged, teachers helped students as correctionists in American schools. Meanwhile, speech and language disorders were dealt with by elocutionists who worked to correct speech disorders and doctors who dealt with speech disorders caused by damage to an organ (Gleissner, 2018).

1.3. Mapping the Current Services in Türkiye

In addition to being a new discipline worldwide, the field is in its infancy in Türkiye. The field's emergence dates back to the 1980s at Hacettepe University, where the program "Audiology and Speech Disorders" was founded to analyze the relationship between audiology and speech development. 'Audiology' and 'speech disorders' were recognized as two distinct disciplines internationally, so the first SLT program was launched at Anadolu University in 2000 with a Master's degree program, and the first undergraduate program was established in the same university in 2012 (DKT-UÇEP, 2016).

The relatively recent feature has shaped the current structure and practice in related research in Türkiye; a significant absence of scholarly literature characterizes it, and the fact that explored global issues have yet to be studied. Since its foundation, scholars in the field have researched various issues. However, SLT services include much more than the concrete, measurable, objective components, such as types and frequencies of speech and language disorders, case characteristics, therapist numbers, and settings where this service is provided. In addition, subjective data, such as experiences, working conditions, satisfaction, and

perspectives of SLTs, should not be overlooked. Limited studies explored these objective points in the Turkish literature (Toğram & Güneri, 2019). Many scholars note the inexistence of previous studies on the issues researched in their studies and emphasize their pioneering features. There are no studies conducted on the application of oral-motor exercises in the related literature (Çağlar & Çiyiltepe, 2019). There are no studies conducted on the collaboration between speech-language therapists (SLTs) and dieticians; this study is the first of its kind (Savran & Çiyiltepe, 2022). This is the first study to examine academicians' ethical values in the field (Kocabıyık & Topçuoğlu, 2021). Studies on the knowledge and awareness of selective mutism among SLTs do not exist (Gerçek & Yılmaz, 2022). Several studies in the international literature have attempted to determine the education and clinical knowledge of speech-language therapists (SLTs) in autism; however, no such study has been found in the Turkish literature (Savaş & Toğram, 2013).

On the other hand, some issues have been studied inadequately. The number of open-access postgraduate theses in SLT has reached 154 between 2004 and 2021; the literature review of the Turkish context shows that the number of studies in this period is limited (Oral & Erçikti, 2021). The analysis of related literature reveals that studies have been conducted to identify the views of other healthcare professionals, but these studies are insufficient (Balo et al., 2021). There are not enough studies on the prevalence of speech and language delays in Türkiye (Kayıran et al., 2012). Several studies have examined the role of teachers in speech and language treatments (Uysal & Tura, 2018). Examining the studies related to selective mutism revealed that a few studies have been conducted on the competencies of speech-language therapists (SLTs) in this area (Gerçek & Yılmaz, 2022).

The nascent history of Türkiye and limited literature have hindered its full development and accessibility; systematic gaps restrict the prompt and sufficient provision of SLT services. The main reason for these gaps is an insufficient workforce and an inadequate number of graduates. The SLT service in Türkiye is significantly impacted by its developing features, including a shortage of healthcare professionals, limited service settings, and inadequate distribution of this service across all geographical regions (Toğram & Güneri, 2019). Integrating school-based speech and language therapies into the provision of this service is an alternative to remove these barriers and make substantial progress in similar challenges. However, such an innovation requires much more than the current state. School-based speech and language therapy services in Türkiye are still unavailable due to various factors stemming from a lack of professionals in the field, and it seems impossible as the number of SLTs is not adequate for it (Oğuz et al., 2019).

This research is based on the following research questions:

1. What are the variations across the USA, the UK, Canada, Australia, and Türkiye in speech and language therapy service provision?
2. What are the common barriers to accessing speech and language therapy services in the contexts of these five countries?
3. How does school-based speech and language therapy contribute to the speech and language therapy sessions?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This article examines the provision of school-based speech-language therapy (SLT) services in the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia and compares them to the

need for this service in the emerging SLT context in Türkiye. It highlights the variations and similarities of this service structure, delivery methods, and systems to glean insights for improving it in Türkiye. The researcher determined these countries as having well-established frameworks for providing SLT services and integrating school-based speech and language therapy services into schools. They provide these services more prevalently and comprehensively than Türkiye. SLTs in these countries assist individuals with speech, language, communication, and swallowing disorders in various settings, including schools, health centers, prisons, and nursing homes. In contrast, SLTs in Türkiye provide services for the same impairments in a few settings, such as special rehabilitation centers or hospitals. Moreover, these countries facilitate school-based therapy practically and effectively, which is not currently available in Türkiye (Oğuz et al., 2022).

SLT services vary across countries, evolving with unique strengths and challenges. Comparing these systems offers valuable insights. Key factors such as historical development, the policies and provision of SLT, the prevalence of speech and language disorders, the demand, number of professionals and workforce shortage in the field, and the barriers to the implementation of these services will shed light on the variations, commonalities among these countries and bridge the gaps in Türkiye to enhance these services aligning with global standards. While the factors affecting the provision and quality of this service are studied overwhelmingly internationally, national studies are mainly based on stakeholders' attitudes, perceptions, and anxiety in the process (Topbay, 2021).

This study examines the health systems of multiple countries for service delivery of SLT and proposes school-based SLT as a strategy to enhance service provision. Therefore, it employs a qualitative comparative approach based on document analysis and systematic literature review. The data sources include articles, government documents, statistical reports, and professional guidelines. Document analysis serves as a needs assessment by drawing on various sources, such as occupational descriptions and reports, to demonstrate similarities and differences (Watkins et al., 2012). Comparative studies offer a deeper understanding of health systems, which are already complex to describe and analyze thoroughly. When the universal health coverage of a field is analyzed in detail, its application in a country or region can be more appropriate for the targeted health system there.

Comparative research evaluating policies, practices, and systems across different settings enables the practical evaluation of policies, practices, and systems in various contexts. It provides inductive and deductive insights into the health system by highlighting similarities, differences, and universal challenges (Esser & Vliegthart, 2017; Healy et al., 2018). Comparative analysis enables researchers to conclude by examining similarities and differences. Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) integrates contextual knowledge and identifies patterns across cases, examining various combinations of reasons contributing to an outcome (Scholz et al., 2016). The primary aim of qualitative comparative analysis is to evaluate various combinations of conditions in terms of their presence or shortage that lead to specific outcomes (Scholz et al., 2016; Smela, 2021). This method is well-suited for investigating the factors and their dynamics and proposing improved practices relevant to the Turkish context.

2.2. Data Collection

The researcher collected data through multiple structured stages to comprehensively analyze related documents. This process started with selecting data from reputable academic databases, such as Scopus, ProQuest, and ULAKBİM (Turkish Academic Network and

Information Centre), to identify relevant articles and publications in the SLT field. The search was extended to journals including Web of Science, International Journal of Public Health, Child Language Teaching and Therapy, Public Health Research & Practice, Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research, Taylor and Francis Online, SpringerLink, International Journal of Language and Communication Disorders, Australian Journal of Teacher Education, International Journal of Speech-Language Pathology, Journal of Public Health, Maternal and Child Health Journal, and SAGE Journals. Moreover, official guidelines, reports, and policy documents from prominent sources like the Bercow Report, World Bank Publications, Journal of Speech, Language, and Swallowing Research, Turkish Association of Speech and Language Therapists (TSTDER), Australian Early Development Census, and Senate Community Affairs References Committee were examined to collect the related data. The documents were selected based on their relevance to the service provision policies and barriers to accessing this service in Canada, Australia, the UK, the USA, and Türkiye. The sources highlighting similarities and variations across these countries were prioritized. The sources that emphasize the contributions of school-based speech and language therapy services to excelling at service provision and barrier removal were screened in selected countries.

2.3. Data Analysis

The data was collected qualitatively by systematically comparing the contexts and related components in the selected countries. By integrating various data sources and employing a comparative approach, this analysis aims to develop feasible practices for creating more effective, equitable, sustainable, and accessible school-based speech and language therapy services, particularly in Türkiye. Thematic analysis (TA) is employed to identify, analyze, and interpret meaning patterns of qualitative data. It provides a systematic procedure for organizing and reporting the researcher's analyses (Clarke & Braun, 2017). This method was applied to categorize the findings according to their familiarity under categories such as historical development, service provision, accessibility, and availability of SLT services, including workforce shortages, geographical and financial barriers, and waiting lists in each country. Then, a comparative analysis was conducted to emphasize similarities, differences, strengths, and gaps in providing this service across these contexts. This structured yet flexible approach ensured a detailed exploration of related data, offering more professional practices in the face of reform gaps in these countries.

3. Findings

3.1. Findings Related to the First Research Question

3.1.1. The history and settings of the service

The SLT field's historical development varies in each country's context. In the UK, SLT emerged as a discipline at the intersection of medicine and education in 1910 (Pearson, 1995). In the United States, the first recorded mention of the speech and language profession appeared in 1897, when it was primarily referred to as "speech correctionist" in a teacher's manual. Afterward, it was officially established by ASHA in 1925 (Blosser, 2024). In Australia, the SLT field was established by Mrs. Elinor Wray in 1931 and emerged through the twentieth century (Hewat, 2022). In Canada, the SLT department started in Quebec in 1933 and expanded to the other provinces in the 1950s (Lagace et al., 2023). Among these countries, Türkiye has the shortest history, with its earliest traces of recognition dating back to the 1980s and its establishment as a postgraduate program in 2000 (Oral & Erçaktı, 2021).

This extended history of SLT services in the UK, the USA, Australia, and Canada has enabled these countries to refine and promote their approaches over time, resulting in diverse settings where this service is provided or integrated. This well-established history has made SLT an essential part of healthcare, education, and community service systems, ensuring its effectiveness and achievability. On the other hand, Türkiye, with its relatively short history in the field, faces significant challenges in providing this service. It is confined to private settings and urban centers, leaving numerous gaps, especially for individuals in disadvantaged areas of the country. This disparity demonstrates the need for more comprehensive, equitable, and widely accessible therapeutic interventions.

Table 1.

Delivery of speech and language therapy service settings across countries

Service delivery settings	
The USA	Educational settings, universities, community centers, private clinics, specialized services, diagnostic services, hospital or home-bound intervention, parent training clinics, self-contained classrooms, resource rooms, approved private schools, and after-school and summer programs (Blosser, 2024; Farquharson et al., 2022; Phelps, 1974)
The UK	Courtrooms, young offender institutions, prisons, hospitals, nurseries, primary and secondary schools, mainstream and special schools, community clinics, community health centers, hospital wards, centers for kids, outpatient departments, clients' homes, assessment units, day centers, clients' residences (Anderson et al., 2022; Pring et al., 2012; Yildirim, 2019)
Australia	Private clinics, schools, pediatric outpatient settings such as hospitals, community health centers, institutions for pre-school education, homes, local centers and centers for people with special needs, tertiary provider universities, community health services, centers for rehabilitation, elderly-care centers, home, the justice system, early childhood intervention centers, and aged-care setting for residential (Conway et al., 2022; Senate Community Affairs References Committee, 2014; Verdon et al., 2011)
Canada	Hospitals, public health units, community health centers, schools, private practices, long-term care and nursing homes, childcare facilities, patient or client homes, corporate settings, correctional facilities, professional associations, regulatory bodies, universities and colleges, and government departments, the justice system of the youth (Anderson et al., 2022; Lagace et al., 2023)
Türkiye	Special education and rehabilitation centers, speech and language therapy centers, private clinics, private and public hospitals, university hospitals, and universities (Kocabiyık & Demirci, 2021)

Schools are at the forefront of addressing children's communication and language impairments and enhancing service provision in these settings. The interventions in the school setting offer more than just an interaction between a therapist and a child. School-based speech and language therapy differs from traditional speech therapy in that it should be strongly aligned with educational paradigms for effective service delivery (Lynch et al., 2020).

3.1.2. The provision and provider policies of speech and language therapy services

Each country has its own healthcare system, funding mechanism, and professional regulation in the provision of this service. Primary care and community services are available in the UK for early identification and intervention. Mild cases are treated, while more severe ones are referred to specialized centers, such as hospitals. These centers relieve the burden on the rest of the system (RCSLT, 2023). In the United States, SLT services are primarily provided in free schools, and appropriate education for individuals with impairments is a priority. SLTs evaluate

and design interventions and then write a report on them. They also provide services in health-related settings (Farquharson et al., 2022; Blosser, 2024). Canada has a pediatric system that assesses speech and language disorders. It is known as Ontario's Preschool Speech and Language Program (SSLP), which is publicly funded. It aims to support children from birth to a specific age in developing their communication skills before entering school. The system offers group and individual consultations and parent or society training (Cunningham & Rosenbaum, 2015). In Australia, when a school-aged child experiences a speech disorder, they receive funding according to the severity of their problems. An SLT is employed to support this child during and out of school. This professional visits a school and organizes individual and consultation therapies (Glover et al., 2015; Commonwealth of Australia, 2014; Senate Community Affairs References Committee, 2014; Cronin, 2017). Türkiye has private rehabilitation centers where students get limited service, and school-based speech and language therapy services are unavailable (Durmaz, 2023; Toğram & Güneri, 2019).

3.1.3. The prevalence of speech, language, and communication disorders

Rapid societal changes and technological advancements have contributed to the prevalence of speech and language impairments. Prolonged exposure to passive screen time, reduced engagement in creative and interactive activities such as storytelling or imaginative play, and preoccupied parents or caregivers with technological devices can limit meaningful interactions in children's early language development. Communication impairments are among the most prevalent disabilities in children (Blosser, 2024; McCormack & Verdon, 2015). In addition to these, the growing number of elderly with acquired speech and language disorders because of an illness like stroke and dementia and disabled children has increased the need for rehabilitation services (Tran et al., 2008; Yoder, 1990). In Türkiye, approximately 3.5% of the population has some form of speech and language impairment (Toğram & Güneri, 2019).

3.1.4. Awareness of stakeholders

The stakeholders include parents or caregivers, teachers, school administrators, doctors, and allied health service staff, whose awareness level significantly determines their ability to recognize and intervene in speech and language disorders. The initial stage of accessing SLT services is raising families' awareness of speech and language impairment. Some potential barriers, such as a lack of awareness of the service's significance, insufficient parental awareness of the language/literacy development of their children, and unawareness of parents of the types of intervention, restrict its availability (McAllister et al., 2011; Parish & Cloud, 2006; Law et al., 2017). Parents' awareness of SLT services and audiology is around 60% when they first meet a professional from the field (Mahendra et al., 2009). In the UK, public health services include Communication Champion Training, which supports Speech and Language Therapists (SLTs) in communicating with parents about their children's development (Law et al., 2017). In Türkiye, some parents hold the idea that 'the child speaks anyway' or 'his father spoke late, too,' so they do not take these disorders seriously, which limits the accessibility of this service for individuals (Kayıran et al., 2012).

3.1.5. Growing demand for speech and language therapists

The need for assistance and guidance for speech-language therapists (SLTs) is increasing steadily and globally due to demographic shifts, the growing prevalence of communication impairments, evolving healthcare policies, and the need to raise awareness of this challenge. In the UK, the number of acquired language disorders stemming from age and early identification increases the need for speech and language therapists (SLTs), which is likely to

continue increasing in the future (RCSLT, 2023). Several factors in the USA contribute to the demand for SLTs, and the shortage will worsen if the number of SLPs does not increase significantly (Squires, 2013). In Canada, there is an increasing demand for graduates in the field; however, the number of them remains inadequate due to a lack of professionals to supervise them (Armstrong, 2021). The exact demand for SLTs is not apparent in Australia; however, it exceeds the supply (Commonwealth of Australia, 2014; McGill & McLeod, 2020). In Türkiye, SLT is a developing field. The number of therapists is limited and not evenly distributed across the country's regions. The number of graduates increases yearly, yet this does not meet the demand (Durmaz, 2023).

3.1.6. The number of speech and language therapists in these countries

The demand for SLTs exceeds the number of graduates in these countries, especially in Türkiye. In the UK, the Royal College of Speech and Language Therapists (RCSLT) is the professional institution for speech and language therapy services, with nearly 20,000 members (RCSLT, 2023). In the USA, 79,104 SLTs serve students aged 3-21 through the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA). They provide services in various settings, and it is planned to increase the number of SLTs in the USA by 19% between 2022 and 2032, resulting in 33,100 new professionals in the field (ASHA, 2024). The American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA) has 19,800 members, including speech-language therapists (SLTs), audiologists, and researchers (Gleissner, 2018). In Canada, 1924 audiologists and 9698 SLTs were registered nationwide in 2017 (Lagace et al., 2023). In Australia, there are nearly 14,000 members of Speech and Pathology Australia (SPA). However, not all therapists are members of this association, and only half of the registered speech-language therapists (SLTs) work in public services (McLeod et al., 2023). In Türkiye, approximately 2,500 speech-language therapists (SLTs) serve individuals with speech and language disorders. In Europe, one SLT serves approximately 6,266 people, while in Türkiye, one SLT provides service for every 28,260 people (Kapadokya University website, 2023).

3.2. Findings Related to the Second Research Question

The factors in Figure 1 have complex interconnections, each affecting or leading to the other. Meanwhile, each plays a key role in addressing practical issues in professional discourse and contributes to specific outcomes in service delivery.

Figure 1. The Interrelated Relationships and Barriers within SLT Services

3.2.1. Workforce Shortages

There is a growing demand for SLT services, especially in disadvantaged parts of countries or cities. Besides, they are influenced by the challenges caused by the insufficient number of professionals. In the USA, there is a shortage of SLTs, partly stemming from the limited number of programs for SLT, the increasing need for these experts, the widening scope for practices, and the aging population. Schools are the places experiencing this shortage the most (ASHA, 2024; Farquharson et al., 2022; Squires, 2013). In the UK, the availability of specialist speech and language therapists (SLTs) is currently limited, and this is likely to remain the case in the future (RCSLT, 2023; Pearson, 1995). The current demand exceeds the number of speech and language graduates in Canada, resulting in a national shortage of competent professionals (Armstrong, 2021; Lagace et al., 2023). In Australia, the limited availability of specialists in the workforce for SLT services is much more effective in rural and isolated areas than in urban areas (Theodoros, 2012). In Türkiye, the number of individuals requiring SLT services and the number of professionals providing these services do not align (Durmaz, 2023; Toğram & Güneri, 2019). As the need for SLT services surpasses the number of SLTs, child development specialists provide services to alleviate speech and language disorders and challenges (Durmaz, 2023; Savran & Çiyiltepe, 2022).

3.2.2. Quality and equity in service provision

The equal availability of health services tailored to each member's exact needs creates equity, ensuring high-quality and efficient therapeutic outcomes. The concept of equal health opportunities is grounded in the principle of human rights, which is rooted in the rejection of discrimination. This equality refers to distributing and planning all supplies, procedures, and programs that affect health services (Law et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2002). However, equity in providing SLT services remains challenging, especially in geographically disadvantaged areas with limited access to competent therapists. In the USA, the health service provided for disabled people is not equal because of the inaccessibility of physical equipment and healthcare settings, the long waiting periods, and unequal service provision for people from various origins, sexes, races, and impairments, which is discriminatory for individuals in the society (McGregor, 2020).

3.2.3. The accessibility and availability of the service

Effective and timely intervention requires both accessibility and availability. According to human rights, every individual who requires health services should have access to them promptly. Additionally, individuals requiring communicative assistance must be guided on accessibility (Bercow, 2008; McAllister et al., 2011; McCormack & Verdon, 2015). Many individuals living in rural, remote, and underserved parts delay the diagnosis or treatment of their speech and language disorders because of inaccessible or unavailable services. Various social, economic, environmental, and political factors contribute to unequal service access (Conway et al., 2022; McCormack et al., 2015; Verdon et al., 2011). The growing demand for SLTs, combined with the insufficient number of graduates in the field and the unaffordability of private services, limits addressing these issues. (Just et al., 2022). In the UK, the “postcode lottery” expression highlights the disparity among the UK districts. At the same time, interventions in some areas are regular but rare for other districts (Bercow, 2008). In Türkiye, parents face the barrier of inaccessibility to SLT services (Topbay, 2021).

3.2.4. Geographical barriers

The lack of professionals in rural and remote areas affects the provision of this service, causing nearly all the barriers in the process to occur. The inadequate or limited public

service, unavailable personal transportation, and the combination of these variables with socioeconomic status prevent people in rural parts of Australia from accessing SLT services (Just et al., 2022; Verdon et al., 2011; Wales et al., 2017; Wilson et al., 2002). As a result, logistical barriers shape the quality of this service in vast distances and underdeveloped countries (Bercow, 2008). In the UK, nearly 50% of youngsters from lower socioeconomic surroundings are more likely to have speech and language disorders than their peers from higher socioeconomic populations (Bercow, 2008). The number of children who are vulnerable or at risk in the rural parts of Australia is high, but access to specialized, therapeutic services for SLT is limited (Wales et al., 2017). In Türkiye, individuals living near or in a city with SLTs can be considered fortunate. However, those living far from this service must travel long distances or give up on receiving the therapy altogether (Toğram & Güneri, 2019). The residents living in the Western parts of the USA have less chance to get services for their speech and language disorders (Morgan et al., 2017).

3.2.5. Financial barriers

Financial issues constitute significant barriers to low-income populations accessing SLT services, as they cannot afford the high cost of private sessions (Parish & Cloud, 2006; Sciberras et al., 2015). They primarily postpone receiving this service when they lack comprehensive insurance and face a shortage of school-based SLT services. The affordability of SLT increases the availability of this service in capital cities while it decreases in remote or rural parts of a country (Cronin, 2017; Just et al., 2022; Ruggero et al., 2012). The overall healthcare expenses of a child with speech and language impairments are significantly higher than currently estimated in the literature (Cronin et al., 2017).

3.2.6. Long waiting lists

Waiting lists can cause individuals to miss out on the chance for early intervention. Children miss the critical periods for intervention, experience uncertainty, and frustration, which causes considerable psychological stress, and feel demotivated to continue sessions (McGill et al., 2020). In the UK, the number of adults on the waitlist is 18,869, with 3,346 individuals needing to wait for a year before the intervention, while the number of children is 65,871, with 20,048 who need to wait for a year before the intervention (Bercow, 2008; RCSLT, 2023). The waiting lists for SLT services in rural districts are typically very long due to time constraints, financial constraints, and staff shortages (RCSLT, 2023). In Australia, the long waitlists are indicators of the demand for SLT services (Commonwealth of Australia, 2014). In Türkiye, children with speech and language disorders usually take their first intervention between 0 and 6 weeks, while this process can expand to over 37 weeks in some cases (Konca, 2021).

3.3. Findings Related to the Third Research Question

In educational settings, SLTs provide targeted support for students in identifying, assessing, and addressing their difficulties. Their role extends beyond an essential therapy because the collaboration they create between themselves and the other process stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, and other professionals, to implement strategies contributes to students' everyday learning. They help students reach their full potential in communication, minimize or overcome barriers in the classroom, enhance their competencies, adapt to the school and classroom atmosphere, and increase readiness for each stage in life without any cost (ASHA, 2000).

3.3.1. School-based speech and language therapies to remove barriers

To remove barriers to SLT services and reduce the number of “missed children,” providers must identify potential barriers and explore alternative solutions (Public Health England, 2020). School-based speech and language therapies ensure equitable access to this service, removing many barriers stemming from ineligibility (Daniel & McLeod, 2017). They contribute to children’s academic performance because they can be integrated into the educational objectives. Therapists provide both language rehabilitation services and professional support for language instruction to keep pace with the classroom curriculum, help students maximize their potential, and foster emotional development (Blosser, 2024; Gleissner, 2018; Lee et al., 2021; Uysal & Gülşah, 2018).

When children start nursery, first, and second grade, they may exhibit some phonological difficulties; however, some can overcome these challenges through years of exposure to the school environment. On the other hand, some of them need intervention to proceed. The SLTs in the school setting differentiate between these two cases (Blosser, 2024; Squiers, 2013). SLTs can assist educators in promoting four language skills, and the presence of an SLT in the educational setting benefits students and teachers (ASHA, 2000; Blosser, 2024). In Australia, the lack of speech-language therapists (SLTs) in educational settings presents a challenge for parents in accessing and maintaining SLT services (Daniel & McLeod, 2017).

As a result of the invaluable contributions of school-based speech and language therapy services, speech-language therapists (SLTs) began to provide services in schools. In 1910, school-based speech and language therapy was established as a significant endeavor, paving the way for its recognition in other settings (Blosser, 2024). In the 1930s, SLT services were provided only in Quebec, Ontario, and Manitoba via government-funded hospitals and schools (Lagace et al., 2023). In the UK, speech, language, and occupational therapy services have been provided in educational settings since the 1980s (Lynch et al., 2020). In Australia, there is a lack of speech and language pathology services in school settings (Daniel & McLeod, 2017; McAllister et al., 2011). In some parts of Australia, school-based speech and language therapy is available or prevalent; in others, this service is provided either infrequently or not at all (Community Affairs References, 2014). No speech and language therapists in an educational context exist in Türkiye (Kement, 2019; Oğuz et al., 2022).

The absence or inadequateness of SLT services in Türkiye and Australia creates similar difficulties in these countries. They rely on external or private healthcare systems, often lacking readily available intervention within the school setting. To improve service provision, SLT services should be integrated into the school system, or SLTs should visit schools to inform teachers about speech and language disorders (Oğuz et al., 2022). In the United States, 57% of speech-language therapists (SLTs) work in educational settings; an SLT is employed in nearly every school. In Türkiye, 32.14% of SLTs provide services in rehabilitation centers. In Türkiye, SLTs do not participate actively in state schools, which is impossible due to the existing system (Kement, 2019; Oğuz et al., 2019).

3.3.2. Collaboration among the stakeholders of the process

The collaboration in the school-based speech and language therapy system encompasses who (the target population), what (the intervention strategies), when (the continuum of service), where (the appropriate setting), and how (the approach to collaboration) (Blosser, 2024). SLTs, teachers, and parents set goals, environment, and other components of the intervention and define barriers to achieve the service together to improve the understanding

of the disorder with desire and alliance (Bercow, 2008; Blosser, 2024; Daniel & McLeod, 2017; Gleissner, 2018; Glover et al., 2015). The cooperation among health, education, disability, and justice sectors plays a crucial role in providing holistic, accessible, and equitable services for all children (Anderson et al., 2022; Glover et al., 2015; McCormack & Verdon, 2015). Their care contributes to early intervention, and their perceptions shape the process (ASHA, 2000; Bercow, 2008; Law et al., 2017). Early intervention aims to provide each child with high-quality early learning experiences and offer the necessary support on time, which requires the collaborative effort of stakeholders (Oğuz et al., 2022).

3.3.3. Early intervention

Early intervention for speech and language disorders can alleviate their long-term effects, enabling children to keep pace with the physical and psychological milestones of their developmental stages. It significantly contributes to critical periods in the development of language disorders. It plays a crucial role in preventing future problems, such as challenges related to behaviors, psychology, and emotions, as well as reducing the likelihood of job opportunities and sometimes leading to criminal liability (Bercow, 2008; Kayıran et al., 2012; McCormack & Verdon, 2015). It is beneficial for children and parents as they can be aware of their children's difficulties earlier and increase the frequency of therapy at an earlier stage (Glover et al., 2015). In the UK, the Early Years Foundation Stage is a framework that evaluates the development of children from birth to the end of the first year of schooling until they are five years old (Bercow, 2008). In the USA, IDEA aims to increase awareness of early intervention services for communication enhancement (Carnes, 2012). In Australia, public-funded early intervention services are provided through public hospitals, community health centers, and other facilities, generally accessible at no cost to the user at the point of contact (Verdon et al., 2011). School-based speech and language therapies complement early intervention and significantly enhance its outcomes by extending its natural reach (Bishop et al., 2017; Blosser, 2024).

3.3.4. The dosage and intensity of sessions

The optimal frequency and intensity vary depending on each individual's case factors, so they must be tailored to their needs and delivered accordingly. Treatment for speech and language impairments is effective when it provides intensive sessions tailored to the specific needs of patients (Blosser, 2024; Enderby & Emerson, 1996). Parents feel more pleased when their children receive regular and frequent therapy (Wilson et al., 2002). School-based speech and language therapy services provide the context for providing appropriately tailored individual sessions within the constraints of educational settings. They contribute to the professional collaboration between teachers and SLTs in a natural environment, and in turn, they help the needs of students more visibly and clearly. They are also adaptable to school culture because they are flexible within the school context (Terreberry et al., 2021).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This qualitative comparative analysis examines the similarities and differences in SLT services across five countries: the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and Türkiye. It considers the strengths and weaknesses of these systems, with a particular emphasis on Türkiye's unique challenges. The findings revealed the critical importance of systematic reforms prioritizing an equal, accessible, and sustainable service provision model in Türkiye. The barriers and disparities that are highlighted in this study are mainly determined through the detailed analysis of the SLT service provision in these countries, with relatively less

emphasis on the case of Türkiye because, besides being a recent field all around the world, SLT is still in its infancy in Türkiye, which limits the amount of available data. They include workforce shortages, quality, equity, accessibility, availability of the service, geographical and financial barriers, and long waiting lists. The acute shortage of professionals in the field and the inexistence of school-based speech and language therapies deteriorate the occurrence of these barriers in Türkiye and widen the service gaps.

The lengthy historical background of SLT in some countries provides a well-established and advanced system for this service, which expands the settings offered in the USA, the UK, Canada, and Australia but remains limited to Türkiye. Despite the persistence of these barriers in these contexts, their severity decreases through the delivery of this service in schools where SLT is integrated into the educational framework. Embedding this service within the education system can transform its delivery into a more equitable, achievable, sustainable, consistent, and natural form through which geographical, accessibility, and financial barriers can be removed. School-based speech and language therapies contribute to interdisciplinary collaboration among the stakeholders in the educational process, provide holistic assistance for children's academic, social, and emotional development, and create an environment for early intervention. The unique challenges in the Türkiye context require tailored approaches, one of which is the implementation of school-based speech and language therapies. This system should be adopted and adapted to the nascent infrastructure of this field.

The implementation of this model necessitates some incentives, such as expanding the training programs for SLT professionals. The strong relationship between SLT and the linguistics field can be facilitated to enhance service availability. In the 1960s, the growing awareness of communication disorders increased the popularity of the Linguistics department in the field. Linguistics underwent considerable changes, especially in the 1970s. By 1978, Manchester University had appointed qualified academicians to the linguistics department to teach SLT courses (Stansfield, 2020).

Public awareness of speech and language impairments should be increased, and the stakeholders in the process should be educated. Future teachers of any language, mainly English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in this context, should receive training on communication disorders as part of their professional development. Additionally, teachers should receive professional development training, and programs and resources should be readily available when they enter the workforce (McAllister et al., 2011). The curricula at higher institutions should be enhanced. Adjustments to the curriculum and additional support are necessary to improve educational outcomes for students with speech and language disorders (McKinnon et al., 2007). Curriculum adjustments in teacher education cater to the diverse needs of individuals with disabilities. When teachers are equipped with the required competencies, they can assist in identifying and intervening the impairments. Policy-makers need to assess the crucial need for additional support for students with communication impairments in school settings; SLTs can be employed, teachers can receive professional development on the issue, and funding opportunities for this assistance can be increased (McLeod & McKinnon, 2010). By prioritizing inclusive approaches, these authorities can remove the gaps and barriers in service provision.

Cross-national studies to explore similarities and differences in various contexts provide valuable insights into the most efficient models for high-quality service provision. The lessons drawn from the experiences of other countries create a more global approach. While

this study comprehensively explores the process components, some limitations, such as country-specific nuances, limited exploration of local policies, reliance on secondary data sources, and analysis of only five countries, may not fully represent the global picture of SLT provision. Further research can be tailored to provide more in-depth and detailed process information.

Authors' Note

This study is based on the data derived from the first author's doctoral dissertation under the supervision of the second author.

Ethical Issues

The authors declare that this study does not require ethics committee approval in accordance with the research integrity regulations of their country as it does not involve any human participants (Date 26/03/2025).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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